

BOOKLET ON GENERATION OF CONFIGURATIONS-DATA MODULE FOR YERITH-ERP-9.0

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Yerith R&D

Yerith-erp-pgi platiNum business Workflow

Figure 1: YERITH-ERP-9.0 BUSINESS Workflow

Figure 2: YERITH-ERP-9.0 COMPONENTS Workflow

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Yerith-erp-pgi platiNum COMPONENTS Workflow

Abstract

THIS document explains mainly how to generate configurations data for Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP; [PGI in French language]) software YERITH-ERP-9.0; from the command line, on a Debian Linux programming environment.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter shows how to generate the debian package named 'yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb' (or 'yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data.deb' as FRENCH-language version) for configuring the ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0.

1.1 Prerequisite Software

Table 1.1: Prerequisite software.

Software	Versions
gdebi	0.9.5.7 + nmu5

Table 1.2: Files required for installation of YERITH-ERP-9.0.

FILES
"yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb"
"yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb"
"yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon.deb"

Table 1.2 illustrates files required for installing YERITH-ERP-9.0.

1.2 A Package management file For Debian Linux

A software system and / or module could be installed easily for the **Debian Linux platform** (<https://www.debian.org>) when its is packaged (archived) as file type '.deb' (or debian package).

Such a '.deb'-file contains files and binary executable and / or instructions on how to place them onto the file system of the computer where to install this software system, and / or program.

1.3 How to Download YERITH-ERP-9.0 sample FOSS source code

1.) From the website "www.github.com" (<https://www.github.com>):

From your bash shell command, type the following command :

```
git clone https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0
```

1.4 Set a BASH-path for YERITH-ERP-9.0 commands

1.) Open a "bash-terminal"

2.) type following lines of Bash-shell code in your '/home/\$USER/.bashrc file':

```
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu
export GIT_EDITOR=vim
QT_SELECT=5
YERITH_ERP_3_0_HOME_FOLDER=${HOME}/yerith-erp-9-0
YERITH_ERP_3_0_PROPERTIES_CONFIGURATION_FOLDER=${YERITH_ERP_3_0_HOME_FOLDER}
YERITH_ERP_3_0_SYSTEM_DAEMON_HOME_FOLDER=${HOME}/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon
PATH=${YERITH_ERP_3_0_HOME_FOLDER}/yerith-erp-9-0-development-scripts:${PATH}
PATH=${YERITH_ERP_3_0_HOME_FOLDER}/yerith-erp-9-0-development-scripts/ENGLISH:${PATH}
export PATH
```

PLEASE, revert the BASH-settings afore given when re-installing your productive version of YERITH-ERP-9.0 so to avoid collisions of BASH environment variables specifications !

1.5 How to generate 'yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.deb'

1.) Open a "bash-terminal"

2.) type following command :

```
yerith-create-dpkg_yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH.sh
```

1.6 How to generate 'yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data.deb'

1.) Open a "bash-terminal"

2.) type following command :

```
yerith-create-dpkg_yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data.sh
```


Chapter 2

Installation of a '.deb' File

This chapter shows how to Install a "debian" package management file.

Figure 2.1: Gdebi-gtk user graphical interface.

2.1 Automated Installation with gdebi-gtk and gdebi

Program gdebi and its Graphical User Interface (GUI) version gdebi-gtk enables one to install a 'deb' file without any troubles and / or configuration of a "debian" software packages repository (as for instance in file "/etc/apt/source.list").

gdebi and gdebi-gtk have following advantage : BOTH programs will search all required dependent packages–programs and will install them automatically for you.

THUS, in this occasion you need to configure your "debian" software packages repository file located at "/etc/apt/source.list".

2.2 Installation of gdebi-gtk and / or gdebi

- 1.) Open a "bash-terminal"
- 2.) type following command to install gdebi-gtk :

```
apt -y install gdebi-gtk
```

- 3.) type following command to install gdebi :

```
apt -y install gdebi
```

2.3 Installation with gdebi

- 1.) Open a "bash-terminal"
- 2.) type following command :

```
gdebi -n yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb
```

2.4 Installation with gdebi-gtk

- 1.) Open a "bash-terminal"
- 2.) type following command :

```
gdebi-gtk yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH.deb
```

- 3.) press button "Install Package".

2.5 *Installation of a Debian Software Repository locally on your Computer*

1.)

2.6 *Installation with apt Tool*

1.) **Prerequisite : You could add all '.deb' into a software "debian" repository online.**

2.) Open a "bash-terminal"

3.) type following command :

```
apt -y install yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH
```

4.) type following command :

```
apt -y install yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH
```

o **Or alternatively to the 2 previous commands, you could issue the following command :**

```
apt -y install yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-configurations-data-ENGLISH yerith-erp-9-0-standalone-ENGLISH
```


Chapter 3

Brief Overview of Configuration Data for YERITH-ERP-9.0

This chapter shows a structure view of how configuration data for YERITH-ERP-9.0 are organized.

Figure 3.1: **Screenshot of configuration data in administrative section of YERITH-ERP-9.0.**

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Table 3.1: Types de paramètres de l'application PGI yeritherp et du système d'alertes et de sauvegardes automatisées.

TYPES DE PARAMÈTRES	UTILISATEURS MODIFICATEURS
paramètres locaux	<i>Administrateur, Manager</i>
paramètres serveurs	<i>Manager</i>

Tous les paramètres du PGI yeritherp sont centralisés dans la section "ADMINISTRATION".

Il existe des **paramètres locaux** (enregistrés sur le disque dur de l'ordinateur de l'utilisateur), et des **paramètres serveurs** (enregistrés dans la base de données du PGI yeritherp):

1. Des **paramètres locaux** influencent uniquement des instances du PGI yeritherp dans l'ordinateur de l'utilisateur, et sont modifiables par 1 **Administrateur** ou 1 **Manager**.
2. Des **paramètres serveurs** influencent TOUTES LES INSTANCES DU PGI yeritherp QUI SONT RATTACHÉES AU SERVEUR DE BASE DE DONNÉES EN QUESTION !
Des paramètres serveurs sont modifiables UNIQUEMENT par 1 **Manager**.

Tous les types de paramètres et les utilisateurs responsables de leurs modifications sont illustrés dans le TABLEAU 3.1.

TOUS PARAMÈTRE LOCAL OU SERVEUR EST SOIT:

1. 1 **paramètre de l'application erp (pgi)** (SECTION 3.2)
2. 1 **paramètre du système d'alertes et de sauvegardes automatisées** (SECTION 3.3).

3.2 PARAMÈTRES DE L'APPLICATION ERP (PGI)

Figure 3.2: La fenêtre de paramétrage du PGI yeritherp.

1 paramètre de l'application erp (pgi) yeritherp est 1 valeur qui influence ses comportements du PGI yeritherp lors de son exécution: **le format des reçus ("petit ", "A4 ", ou "A5 ") en est 1 exemple !**

3.2.1 LOCAL parameters — Computer LOCAL specific

3.2.2 Server parameters — BUSINESS-only correlated information

3.3 PARAMÈTRES DU SYSTÈME D'ALERTES ET DE SAUVEGARDE AUTOMATISÉE DE LA BASE DE DONNÉES

Figure 3.3: La fenêtre de paramétrage du système d'alertes, et du système de sauvegarde automatisée.

1 paramètre du système d'alertes, et du système de sauvegarde automatisée YERITH-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON est 1 valeur qui influence ses comportements lors de son exécution: **le répertoire de sauvegarde des bases de données MySQL de yeritherp EN EST 1 EXEMPLE !**

Chapter 4

CONCLUSION

*This chapter concludes our brief presentation on generating "debian" package management files for YERITH-ERP-9.0; for a **Debian Linux** (<https://www.debian.org>) installation environment system.*